

THE INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT POWDER IMPREGNATION PROCESSES ON THE PROPERTIES OF L-SHAPED WOVEN FABRIC REINFORCED PEEK COMPOSITES BY HOT STAMP FORMING

Hansong Liu, Wenkuo Lu, Na Li, Kai Wang, Yan Zhao*, and Shanyi Du
School of Materials Science and Engineering, Beihang University, Beijing 100191, China

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials (ACM) have become the basic materials of the aerospace engineering. Among them, continuous fiber (CF) reinforced poly(ether-ether-ketone) (PEEK) composites have been widely used in the structure of aerospace composite materials due to their advantages of excellent toughness and impact resistance, short processing and forming cycle and outstanding implementability of secondary processing. Among these structures, L-shaped structure is a common structural form. The flexural resistance of L-shaped parts is stronger than that of flat sheet with the same thickness and lamination, and this kind of structure can facilitate the assembly of parts.

The extensive application of L-shaped structure has put forward a lot of requirements for material forming process. For continuous fiber reinforced PEEK composites, hot stamp forming is a high-efficiency and low-cost molding method. Before the deformation step of hot stamp forming, it is necessary to ensure that the high-quality composite flat sheet is obtained. To realize this practical requirement, in this research PEEK composite sheet was prepared by powder impregnation.

Powder impregnation is a method of preparing composite materials by combining powder polymer with reinforced fiber. Scholars have conducted a lot of researches on this method. Based on these researches, CF/PEEK composite fabric laminate was prepared by dry powder impregnation method and wet powder impregnation method. Furthermore, L-shaped PEEK composites were prepared by hot stamp forming. This contrast research is about the defects, shape precision and mechanical properties of L-shaped parts from different impregnation methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

The introduction of materials

PEEK powders were obtained from Changchun Jilin University Special Plastic Engineering Research Co., Ltd, China. Carbon fiber woven fabrics CF3052 (5HS, 3K) were purchased from Weihai Tuozhan Fiber Co. Ltd., China. The emulsifier Triton X-100 (C.P.) was obtained from Xilong Scientific company of China.

Preparation of CF/PEEK composites

In dry powder impregnation process, dry PEEK powders were dusted on fabrics evenly in a steel mold. In wet power impregnation process, CF/PEEK prepregs were obtained following the figure. Composite laminates were obtained with the final fiber volume fraction about 50%-55%.

Preparation of CF/PEEK composites by wet power impregnation process

Preparation of L-shaped CF/PEEK composites

L-shaped CF/PEEK composites were manufactured by hot stamp forming. There were four steps including heating, transfer, stamping and unmolding. The process parameters, such as heating temperature, heating time, transfer time, mold temperature and holding time were designed following previous experiments.

Preparation of L-shaped CF/PEEK composites by hot stamp forming

Optimization of process parameters

A series of experiments were carried out and the method of analysis of variance was used to optimize the process parameters, such as heating temperature, heating time, transfer time, mold temperature and holding time.

No.	Experimental variables					ILSS
	T _{heating}	t _{heating}	T _{transfer}	T _{mold}	t _{hold}	
1	360	2	20	280	1	86.38
2	360	2	20	280	2	89.86
3	360	2	20	280	5	87.41
4	360	3	40	300	1	94.69
5	360	3	40	300	2	86.47
6	360	3	40	300	5	91.74
7	360	5	60	320	1	30.32
8	360	5	60	320	2	58.60
9	360	5	60	320	5	39.04
10	380	2	40	320	1	84.95
11	380	2	40	320	2	88.43
12	380	2	40	320	5	88.44
13	380	3	60	280	1	33.59
14	380	3	60	280	2	81.23
15	380	3	60	280	5	83.04
16	380	5	20	300	1	83.94
17	380	5	20	300	2	85.88
18	380	5	20	300	5	80.61
19	400	2	60	300	1	87.80
20	400	2	60	300	2	83.82
21	400	2	60	300	5	86.17
22	400	3	20	320	1	88.12
23	400	3	20	320	2	87.97
24	400	3	20	320	5	84.20
25	400	5	40	280	1	85.15
26	400	5	40	280	2	86.66
27	400	5	40	280	5	83.37
T ₀	73.83	87.03	86.05	79.63	74.99	
T ₁	78.91	81.23	87.77	86.80	83.22	
T ₂	85.92	70.41	64.85	72.23	80.45	
R _i	12.08	16.62	22.92	14.57	8.23	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The defects and mechanical properties of L-shaped parts

Metallographic method is an appropriate method to detect defects with multiple interlaminar orientations. It can be clearly observed that some defects such as resin-rich area and fiber wrinkles appeared in the corner area of L-shaped parts of composites prepared by both dry and wet powder impregnation method. The mechanical properties of L-shaped parts were evaluated by four-point bending test, which was conducted according to ASTM D6415. The CBS result showed that mechanical properties of L-shaped parts prepared by dry powder impregnation method was higher.

The metallograph of L-shaped composite parts corners and the test of four-point bending test

The shape precision of L-shaped parts

The dimensional change rate showed different situation. At the corner area, due to the impact stress, the width of parts changed 2.3% (dry) and 10.0% (wet). At the same position, the thickness changed 3.3% (dry) and 2.4% (wet). The angle was 91.54° (dry) and 86.36° (wet). The width precision of L-shaped parts by wet powder impregnation process is relatively poor.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we compared the defects, shape precision and mechanical properties of L-shaped parts from different impregnation methods. In general, L-shaped parts from dry powder impregnation showed high quality, but the comprehensive quality of the L-shaped parts from wet powder impregnation can be comparable to it.

Moreover, no matter which kind of impregnation method was chosen, tests of mechanical properties of L-shaped parts showed that corner areas of L-shaped parts was weak areas.

To improve the interlaminar performance of CF/PEEK L-shaped parts corner areas, future work will be focused on interface strengthening and interlayer toughening base on wet powder impregnation method.

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Laboratory production line of CF/PEEK prepregs

CF/PEEK prepregs

Finite element simulation

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